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Investigation on improving the compressive strength of the unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite

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Content

- Development trend of carbon fiber
- Effect of carbon fiber and matrix on the compressive properties of the composites with experiments
- Effect mechanisms on the compressive properties of the composites with theoretical analysis
- Summary

1 Development trend of carbon fiber

Composites reinforced by carbon fibers are indispensable for lightweight structure. It is widely used in industrial fields for the high strength-weight ratio.

1 Development trend of carbon fiber

In aerospace, typical loads for aerospace composites components:

- Compressive load is key model for most aerospace craft.
- But the compressive strength of the composite become the weakness comparing with other properties

1 Development trend of carbon fiber

Manufacturer	Toray				Hexcel			
Matrix	Toughened epoxy				Toughened epoxy			
Carbon fiber	T300	T800H	T1100G	M40J	AS4	IM7	IM10	HM63
Tensile strength (MPa)	1760	2840	3797	2250	2205	2723	3310	2410
Tensile modulus (GPa)	130	160	173	215	141	164	190	255
Tensile fracture elongation (%)	1.3	1.6	/	1.0	1.6	1.6	1.6	0.9
compressive strength (MPa)	1570	1570	1599	1080	1530	1689	1793	1310
compressive modulus (GPa)	125	145	151	205	128	146	164	221
ILSS (MPa)	107	107	115	90	128	128	128	101
Tensile/ compressive raio	0.89	0.55	0.42	0.48	0.69	0.62	0.54	0.54

※Data from the product catalog of Toray and Hexcel Co., published on their official website.

- Tensile properties is higher and higher, but no significant increase for compressive properties
- ILSS decrease with the increase of the modulus, which leads to the decline of the compressive strength

1 Development trend of carbon fiber

Properties comparison of the present composites with high strength carbon fiber and aluminum alloy

Suppliers	Toray		Hexcel		Aluminum alloy
Reinforcement	T300	T800H	IM7	IM10	(Typical data)
Tensile strength(MPa)	542	872	845	1013	500
Tensile modulus(GPa)	46	56	57	67	75
Compressive strength(MPa)	550	550	591	618	550
Compressive modulus(GPa)	44	51	53	57	75

※ Estimated data for carbon fiber/epoxy laminates of [$\pm 45/0/90$]s according to the official product catalog

Properties of IM10 composites increase noticeably; however, **the modulus is still not high enough**

1 Development trend of carbon fiber

3rd Advanced Composite

20's
21 Century

(?)

2nd Advanced Composite

90's
20 Century

(T800/IM7 carbon fibers
High strength and medium modulus)

1st Advanced Composite

60-70's
20 Century

(T300/T700/aramid fiber
High strength, low modulus)

	Tensile	compress	C/T
strength	2840	1570	0.55
modulus	160	145	

	Tensile	compress	C/T
strength	1760	1570	0.89
modulus	130	125	

※ data from Toray's official product catalog

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1 Development trend of carbon fiber

2 Experimental investigation

Theoretical analysis indicates that diameter and alignment of filament, strength of resin are the key factors influencing the compressive strength

Composites Science and technology 2009, 69(7-8):956-964

2 Experimental investigation

Numerical calculation indicated that increasing diameter of filament and enhancing the modulus of the matrix are the effective methods to improve compressive strength based on our materials parameters

Materials parameters

E_f (GPa)	294	V_f	0.6
G_m (MPa)	1200	D_f (μm)	5-6
S_m (MPa)	90		

2 Experimental investigation

Materials

Homemade medium-modulus carbon fiber with different diameter

Homemade high-modulus carbon fiber with different processing

Properties of the resin matrix

(a) 5.0 μm

(b) 5.3 μm

(c) 5.8 μm

(d) 6.0 μm

wet spinning process

dry jet-wet spinning process

$\sigma \sim 5.7 \text{ GPa}$ $E \sim 290 \text{ GPa}$
C content: $\sim 96\%$ w.t.

$E \sim 380 \text{ GPa}$
C content: $> 99\%$ w.t.

	Matrix's tensile strength / Mpa	Matrix's tensile modulus / Gpa
Epoxy 1#	82	3.6
Epoxy 2#	84	4.2
BMI 1#	/	> 4.5

2 Experimental investigation –effect of diameter

Experimental results show that compressive strength is enhanced with the increase of the diameter

Following Standard ASTM D3410

➤ But the increase of the diameter is limited, since it is difficult to maintain the high strength & modulus of the carbon fibers if further increasing the diameter, considering the manufacture processing

2 Experimental investigation

—effect of the type of carbon fiber

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Compressive strength for composites with different carbon fibers

		M40J- Manufacturer's data	Homemade carbon fiber with high modulus 1#	Homemade carbon fiber with high modulus 2#	Homemade carbon fiber with high modulus 3#
Carbon fibers	Manufacturing process	w*	w*	d*	d*
	Tensile modulus/GPa	377	380	384	384
	Sizing amount/%	1.0	1.2	0.7	1.1
	Diameter/ μm	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Carbon fibers reinforced polymer composites	Compressive strength/MPa	1080~1270	1104	670	1151
	Compressive modulus/MPa	/	191	180	216
	Interlaminar shear stress/MPa	90	86	42	90

w* represents the wet spinning process and d* represents the dry jet-wet spinning process.

- For composites with high modulus carbon fibers, the key is to improve the interfacial bonding strength between the carbon fiber and matrix.
- Dry jet-wet spinning process brings high strength, but it is hard to enhance the interfacial bonding, especially for high modulus carbon fiber!

2 Experimental investigation –effect of resin

Carbon fiber	Homemade carbon fiber with medium modulus and large diameter					
	Epoxy 1#		Epoxy 2#		BMI 1#	
	average	Cv/%	average	Cv/%	average	Cv/%
Matrix's tensile modulus/ Gpa	3.6		4.2		>4.5GPa	
Compressive strength/MPa	1500	3.4	1720	2.7	1780	7.1
Compressive modulus/MPa	158	3.2	155	6.3	157	2.0
Interlaminar shear stress/MPa	100	1.8	110		114	2.4

- Composite consisting of fibers with a large diameter and the resin with very a high Young's modulus were fabricated.
- The fibers exhibit the similar mechanical properties with Toray T800H carbon fiber, but the diameter is increased by 20%.
- A kind of resin with the Young's modulus about 4.5 GPa is obtained. The micro-bond between the fibers and the resin maintains a high level.
- As a result, the compressive strength is increased by about 15% so far.

2 Experimental investigation – fiber misalignment

According to Yurgartis' measurement method, the misaligned angle of the fibers are obtained statistically

Fiber Misalignments:

	Average	Standard error	Distribution between -2° ~2°
Carbon fiber/Epoxy	-0.608	1.094	86%
Carbon fiber/BMI	-0.188	0.974	96%

Resin	Toughened epoxy		BMI	
Viscosity	~7Pa`s		~1Pa`s	
ILSS/Mpa	100	1.8	110	2.4

S.W. Yurgartis, *Composites Science and Technology* 30 (1987) 279--293

2 Experimental investigation

Summary of fracture process of compression

Fiber misalignment

Fiber bulking

Stain on matrix and transverse deformation

Cracks of the resin and debonding

Resin yield without ability to hold the fibers

composites fracture with fiber kinking or splitting

Kinking | Splitting

3 Theoretical analysis

FEA model considering the fiber misalignment

- Modeling showing a band of stress concentration.
- Tensile stress and compression stress on each side
- Fracture appearance of the specimen exhibits the type of kinking band, coincident with the modeling

Point A

Yielding

3 Theoretical analysis

Weight of the influence factor with the FEA model

- First of all, the misaligned fiber angle affects the compressive strength.
- When structural parameters determined, fiber's diameter and plastic properties & Young's modulus of resin are key factors influencing the compressive strength of the composites.

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4 Summary

- According to the theoretical analysis, the compressive strength of composites reinforced by unidirectional carbon fibers are strongly influenced by the misaligned angle of fibers, modulus of matrix, interfacial bonding strength and so on.
- Experimental results agree with the calculating ones. And a kind of carbon fiber with large diameter and resin with high modulus are fabricated, based on which the compressive strength of the composite is enhanced by about 15%.
- Next advanced composite should be high strength, high modulus, and compressive-tensile balance, which need new resin with high strength and modulus, and high modulus carbon fiber with enhanced interfacial properties.

4 Summary

Future trend of potential new carbon fiber and new resin

New carbon fiber

$\sigma \sim 5.8\text{GPa}$

$E \sim 380\text{GPa}$

Noticeably increasing the ILSS for high-modulus carbon fiber

New resin

$\sigma \sim 120\text{MPa}$

$E \sim 6\text{GPa}$

Proper processibility for fabricating composites

*Thanks
for your attention!*

